

Chemistry in the Service of India.

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Let me in the first place express my very sincere appreciation of your kindness in unanimously electing me President of the Indian Chemical Society. I feel it to be an honour to succeed so distinguished a predecessor as Sir P. C. Rây, more especially since I can not claim to be one of those who in the words of an American technical chemist, "daily sup with electrons." When such matters as atomic constitution and Werner's theory of co-ordination are under discussion I keep discreetly silent, when the organic chemist not content even with what some of us irreverently term "wire-netting" goes on to describe cage formulae and spiro-compounds I listen with all respect. Nevertheless I have a shrewd suspicion that there are others in my case and I take comfort in the fact that there are large areas of chemical knowledge, especially those concerned with the application of chemistry to the uses of life, which are still within the reach of ordinary mortals. We have to bear in mind that the phenomena of chemistry remain the same though theories develop. It may be doubted whether the extensive knowledge of facts, and diversity of phraseology possessed by the modern student really imply a clearer concept of the colloid state than was possessed by Graham.

It is necessary that we should not confuse knowledge about things with knowledge of the things themselves. It has been suggested by a modern witty philosopher of a more solemn writer, world famous in his day, that had he once encountered a live fact he would have fled screaming. On the other hand the discoverer whose genius more than any other has influenced the externals of our modern life, Michael Faraday, was, I believe, innocent of mathematics, though his clear vision of essentials enabled his theories to be put into mathematical form by Clarke Maxwell.

The bearing of these observations on the subject of my address "Chemistry in the Service of India" will be seen if I mention the

following facts. At the Benares meeting of the Indian Science Congress a discourse was given on the structure of the atom and the large hall of the University was filled. At a symposium on the subject of the true path of Indian industrial development the audience was scarcely more than 20 individuals. In the U. S. A. on the other hand a 20 million dollar fund has been supported by Secretary Hoover to encourage students to take up purely scientific studies at the University, lest the stream of fundamental knowledge should dry up at its source.

In the U. S. A. we hear that the workman drives to his work in a Ford motor car. In India untold millions eke out a bare living on the verge of starvation. This poverty trouble is not confined to tillers of the soil, the difficulties of the Indian middle class are well known. Only a short time ago I was criticising, perhaps a little severely, what seemed to be lack of initiative and originality of thought on the part of an M.A. graduate, and he replied "I am afraid, we are so concerned with merely getting a living that we have no time to think."

How can chemistry help us in the solution of this problem and how in the solution of it can Indian chemists help themselves, is the subject which I desire that we should consider to-day. At this point I should like to emphasise, what has been so well put by Sir P. C. Ray in his note to the report of the Thorpe Commission on the projected Chemical Service, that chemistry in the service of India does not necessarily mean the same thing as Indians in the Chemical Service. Until an increasing number of Indian students of Chemistry are able to earn a living outside of appointments under Government or of subordinate positions in large business concerns, the problem will not be solved nor will chemical science be really applied to the service of this country in any effective way. Moreover, year by year, more and more young students of chemistry are being turned out from the increasing numbers of Universities and Technical Institutes. All of these cannot expect to find Government posts, and already warning voices have been heard from the commercial world that existing mills and factories are nearing saturation point so far as the employment of chemists is concerned. Moreover many of those who are employed cannot be termed anything more than analysts whose prospects are necessarily limited. On the other hand those of a wide training who can really claim to be technical chemists, or at any rate would become such if given

the opportunity, have great difficulty in obtaining suitable employment. Some specially brilliant men have to my great regret forsaken the profession for lucrative employment elsewhere. To arrive at some remedy for this state of affairs we may perhaps usefully consider the situation systematically under the following heads:—

1. Industrial Conditions in India.
2. Chemical Education in India.
3. Existing Outlets for Chemical Students.
4. Future Developments.

1. *Industrial Conditions in India.*

We have to bear constantly in mind the fact that industries, nearly always, have begun as arts, and it is only after a certain stage of development has been reached that the assistance of advanced science is called for.

I myself remember the early days of metallography when under the enthusiastic guidance of Professor Arnold of Sheffield I laboriously polished my sections of iron and steel. Since then this science has been applied to the whole vast industry of special steels and alloys of every description, and in an industrially developed country affords employment for many specially trained men. Outside of Jamshedpur, how many such openings are there in India?

Nevertheless excellent steel was made in Sheffield before the advent of the microscope, mainly because a large population of workers had grown up in whom the knowledge of iron and steel production and working was inbred. It has been for the research chemist to find out by prolonged investigation what the workman means who examines the fracture of a test piece of steel and says there is no 'nature' in it.

Until the chemist is able not only to give scientific descriptions, but also to be responsible for the actual control of a technical process, the possibly illiterate workman, who can actually do things, is the more valuable individual.

I have taken this one example with which I happen to be familiar. Many others may be cited. How many chemists does the textile industry of India support, other than occasional analysts of accessory material such as size, fillers, etc.? We may hope the work of the

Indian Cotton Committee will show the way to extended application of scientific knowledge.

Hides are tanned, lac is grown and manufactured, oil is pressed with little assistance from the chemist. In all these cases I do not for a moment suggest that there is not abundant scope for the application of chemical science, my point simply is that the industries come into existence and carry on at any rate to some profit before thinking about chemists, therefore the chemist has to *prove* his value to the manufacturer.

At this point we must distinguish between a chemist and an analyst. The general public unfortunately has little conception of what the work of a chemist really is, like the steel works manager of old days about whom Professor Arnold told me, who strolled into the laboratory and remarked " 'eres where you does your tests I suppose does 'em wi' drugs I reckon," and who referred to the future scientific leader of the iron and steel industry as " that there chemical."

I have found the best way to bring home the difference between a chemist and a " tester " or " analyser " is to contrast a draughtsman with an engineer. An engineer must be a good draughtsman but a draughtsman is not necessarily an engineer, *i.e.*, he is not primarily responsible for design. As an engineer is one who thinks in terms of engineering so a real chemist is one who " thinks chemically." A technical chemist must even go further and think in terms of technical possibilities, he must possess what I once ventured to describe as " technical sense."

It is now just 10 years ago since I used that expression in my Presidential Address to the Chemical Section of the Indian Science Congress at Lahore and it is of interest to see what the experience of these 10 years has taught.

I am just as certain as ever that no serious progress can be made in the application of science to industry in the absence of men who possess this technical sense. On the other hand it has become clear that the development in India of large scale manufacturing industries, requiring the services of such men will be at a much slower rate than was at one time thought likely owing largely to the absence of an industrial population such as I have referred to in the case, *e.g.*, of Sheffield.

Quite recently I was discussing the possibility of starting a glass factory at a certain locality and the fundamental condition which

made it possible at all was the presence of a number of indigenous glass blowers in the neighbourhood. The glass factory had to be based primarily on their aptitude.

I feel therefore that the industrialisation of India must come gradually by careful utilisation of the material to our hand.

The material we are primarily concerned with is the Indian chemist which brings us to our second matter for consideration, *viz.*

2. *Chemical Education in India.*

Speaking in Calcutta there is no temptation to question the ability of Indians to carry out scientific research of the highest order, it is sufficient to mention the names of Bose, Ráy and Raman. In our *Journal* which I have studied with some care there are contributions which seem to me to be of great value from such workers as Bhatnagar, Ghosh, Mukherjee and B. K. Singh, to mention only a few out of many others, there is therefore small likelihood of the torch of pure scientific inquiry being extinguished in India.

In bio-chemistry, with which I am more familiar I am proud to name among my own students several who have shown themselves more than able to hold their own in competition with workers of their own status in England. Even in purely technological activity, the results of which do not find publication in the ordinary journals, I know of many Indians who are doing excellent work.

All these however are outstanding men, and we have to consider the rank and file, and it is here that the question of education becomes of first importance. I have recently had occasion to interview a number of candidates for admission to courses in technological chemistry, and I have been very much concerned to find how little real knowledge of chemistry is possessed by the ordinary pass B.Sc. Information apparently has been merely swallowed, not assimilated. Too often the candidate complains that it is several months since he passed his examination, therefore he cannot be expected to remember quite simple chemical facts. There appears to be almost complete ignorance of what may be called general knowledge, involving chemical information, such for instance as the composition of glass or pottery, the simple chemistry of plant growth, or the sources of India's coal supply.

It is disconcerting to have to interrupt a lecture to science graduates in order to fill in lacunae in "general knowledge." Chemistry

which is only a matter of memorising formulae and equations is a dead thing of no cultural or vocational value. What is the use of knowing that the formula of potash is KOH if it calls up no mental picture of the actual substance and its properties.

I feel strongly that the whole programme of the teaching of science in our schools and colleges needs revision in the direction of a greater sense of reality. What is required is something of the nature of what used to be called "natural philosophy" which might be defined as the illustration of scientific principles from the world we live in. Such a course was to be found in an excellent handbook for French schools by Paul Bert in which were given in most interesting fashion, with copious illustrations, the elements of botany, zoology, geology, physics and only finally chemistry.

The other day, however, I was glad to learn from an officer in the United Provinces Educational Service that a course of science is to be introduced in the vernacular schools in the U. P., and that in the high schools the concept of science teaching is to be extended along the lines suggested.

Much freer use should be made, I would suggest, of *viva voce* methods in examination.

In this respect the examinations of the Institute of Chemistry, which are designed to discover whether a candidate is a live chemist or only a memoriser, may perform a valuable function now that the examination can be held in India, and every encouragement should be given to students to qualify for the Associateship Examinations.

A sound basis of scientific principles both physical and chemical must precede anything in the nature of advanced technical training, there must in fact be some science present before it can be applied.

This next stage of training, *viz.*, the technical application of scientific principles, is not so easy to arrange for. Just as it is necessary to have some science to apply, so there must be knowledge of practice to which to apply the science, and it is here that the difficulty arises.

In the very frank and valuable address of Sir William Marris at the opening of the recent industrial exhibition in Lucknow he states what we must recognise to be the fact that until we can ourselves carry out a technical process to profit we are only amateurs. No amount of training in the shelter of a Polytechnic or as a temporary apprentice in a works can give that reality of knowledge that comes from experience of actual financial responsibility.

Unfortunately those who are in a position to bring such experience to the service of teaching are often doing better by carrying on their actual business than they could by imparting their knowledge to others. Moreover a first rate technical expert may not equally have the gift of imparting to others the results of his experience.

So we are in danger of a vicious circle, the specially trained student begins to teach before he has proved his ability commercially, his students teach other students and so the original knowledge derived from works experience becomes sadly diluted.

The only way that I see out of this dilemma is that the remuneration for such teaching either by way of salary, or freedom for private practice should be adequate to attract men with real practical experience.

This method is more and more in vogue in Municipal service in England and has been always recognised in the University teaching of Medicine and Law.

3. *Existing Outlets for Chemical Students.*

Granted we have well trained students the problem is still what to do with them. The question may be asked whether in the present state of Indian industry such students can find satisfactory employment. In my judgment, given the requisite product of the training which I have indicated, there should be no difficulty in finding modest outlets for the employment of chemists for some time to come along existing lines. It is encouraging to find from statistics in my possession that although the proportion of chemical students turning to teaching or Government service is still high, there is a distinct increase of late years in the number of those engaged in connection with manufacturing industry. A number of manufacturing concerns have recently employed a trained chemist for the first time and have found that he has more than earned his salary.

Moreover, Government, Railway and Municipal services are finding new work for chemists in connection with such matters as milk and food protection, water supply and sewage purification, and stores control.

There is a large opening for scientifically trained commercial travellers to develop demand for the products of chemical and kindred industries. The extraordinary success of the advertising campaign of the Tea-Planters' Association should stimulate like enterprise in other directions.

I look for a great increase in chemical work in connection with agriculture as soon as the Royal Commission has reported.

More and more it is becoming evident that modern agriculture is a branch of bio-chemistry. The recent work at Rothamsted, Bangalore and Cawnpore on the preparation of artificial farmyard manure opens up quite new possibilities in the application of bio-chemical forces.

The fascinating researches on scientific manuring now in progress at Coimbatore in conjunction with the experiments on animal nutrition at Coonoor have shown the extraordinary influence on the fertility and nutritive value of the seed of the application to the crop of comparatively small amounts of nitrogenous organic matter, while small variations in the mineral constituents of the plant food have been shown greatly to influence the character of the plant products. These results corroborate kindred work at Bangalore on the influence of various fertiliser elements on the growth of the host plants of lac, with consequent effect on the yield and character of the lac produced.

All these, and many other developments of biochemical research indicate that large additions should be made to the research staff of the agricultural departments if the premier industry of India is to reap the fullest benefit of modern discovery.

4. Future Developments.

In the above directions, therefore, are to be found an increasing number of "jobs" for chemists. As was stated at the outset however our efforts to give to India the best service of which chemical science is capable will largely fail unless the rank and file of our chemical students are imbued with the spirit of "creative enterprise" which, to again quote Sir William Marris, is essential for true industrial progress. Every man who can start a paying industry and carry it on of his own initiative is doing the very finest service to his country, as well as building up a happy and independent career for himself. Here will be the test of the reality of the training which our schools and colleges can give, not necessarily a training sufficient to qualify for immediate financial responsibility in industry but at any rate a training in essentials and in the acquirement of the right attitude of mind. It has been said that the young subaltern on receiving his commission is not expected to perform the duties of a general or to be able to devise schemes of strategy and tactics

but at least he should be able to deliver a squad of men at a given place punctually at a given time.

It is this quality of trustworthiness that almost more than anything else is required of the budding industrialist. If he is preparing only a single material let it be always of the quality specified, and always delivered on time. Even in the manufacture of such apparently simple household things as jams or jellies his training, if it has been satisfactory, should enable him to maintain always the same taste and quality, proper keeping properties, neat make up and adequate stock in hand.

I am happy to know that quite a number of chemical students are making their own industrial ventures with success. At the Harcourt Butler Technological Institute the endeavour is being made to ease the initial anxiety of such enterprises by allowing ex-students to make use of the large scale plant at the Institute to prepare soap, express oil or tan hides from their own raw materials, charging a fair price for such service.

It is often queried how can such small ventures compete with modern large concerns. The answer is, because they are small and the overhead charges are correspondingly trifling.

Many world-famous products have originated in back kitchens of small shops. Such I believe was the birth place of McKintosh's toffee and of Crawford's biscuits. Others such as Lazenby's sauce are still made as I have myself seen, in a small room of a big factory.

There is no essential reason therefore why such small factories should not be the precursors in India of real indigenous industries on modern lines.

Especially does this apply to agricultural industries of which much has already been written. The most recent suggestion is the production of egg powder, an industry largely dependent on imports from China which have now greatly diminished owing to the disturbed state of that country. More and more the chemist should help to convert the struggling farm into a flourishing "food factory." Then we shall see realised the fine ideal urged by Lord Irwin of the "scholar ploughman."

It should be the aim of the true agricultural industrialist to economise his forces and machinery as carefully on his farm as the works manager in purely chemical industry.

Some remarkable articles have recently appeared in the valuable little paper edited by Captain J. W. Petavel, known as "Bread and

Freedom," the organ of the movement for dealing with the poverty problem on the lines advocated by that great son of Bengal, Sir Asutosh Mookerjee.

Attention is drawn in these articles to the enormously increased crop yields obtained by the intensive trituration of soil and the transplantation of seedlings by recently invented special machinery, thus indicating the possibilities of a "technified" agriculture.

To illustrate the increase in crop yield which may be obtained if thorough scientific control is exercised, I may perhaps usefully mention an instance within my own experience. Knowing that tomatoes grew like weeds in Nasik and that I could only get 4 annas for a mali basketful in the bazaar, I suggested to a large firm in England the possibility of providing bulk canned tomatoes from India rather than from the United States. I went carefully into costs using very cheap labour and outfit and forwarded a price to London. I was told that I must halve my price per ton before I could compete. The labour and outfit costs could not be reduced, the freight was not excessive, where then was the snag? It appeared that the utmost crop which had so far been raised in Nasik was 9 tons per acre. On consulting the Report of the Intelligence Department of the Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, London, I found that at the Research Station at Waltham Cross a yield of 50 tons of tomatoes per acre had been obtained by the use of thoroughly rotted turf as a manure.

A case is reported in Farmer's Bulletin No. 133 of the U. S. Department of Agriculture where under the best conditions a tomato crop worth Rs. 18,000 has been sold from one acre during a season.

Facts such as these and many others which might be cited, make it clear that if anything like the scientific study and capital outlay was bestowed on agricultural industry, as is given to what may be termed "mechanical" industry, marvellous results would be obtained. The law of diminishing returns would seem, in the light of modern researches, to be much less forbidding than was at one time supposed.

I would urge that here the Indian chemist has an unlimited field for his energies. It seems impossible to conceive that such fascinating work, could for a moment be deemed derogatory to social dignity. Unintelligent monotonous toil may be felt to be unworthy of so called educated people but such work as is possible to the "scholar ploughman" is the most engrossing that can well be conceived, besides

affording possibilities of great increase of material wealth to the individual, to those associated with him and ultimately to the whole country.

In the various directions indicated in the foregoing discourse, I have tried to show the great possibilities of Chemistry in the service of India. In this service there is ample scope for that true patriotism which finds its expression through productive work rather than by emotional rhetoric.*

* Presidential address delivered at the Annual General Meeting of the Indian Chemical Society, Calcutta, on 6th January, 1928.

